

Urban Heat Inequality: Empowering Vulnerable Households in Combating Heat Exposure in their Environments

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1 Abstract

Elevated summertime temperatures disproportionately affect marginalized communities, particularly in urban regions. Generally, urban areas are warmer than rural surroundings, and vulnerable populations tend to reside in densely populated areas with significant heat buildup. Frequent heat exposure, limited resources, and inadequate heat-coping mechanisms among at-risk residents result in adverse effects. This disrupts their sleep, hampers concentration, and limits carrying out valued activities. Additionally, there are other challenges, such as inadequate green spaces, poor air quality, and suboptimal housing conditions, all of which augment the effects for vulnerable populations.

Our research has two objectives: first, we aim to identify vulnerable groups at risk of various heat exposures within their places of residence and their nearby surroundings by uncovering the social and spatial inequalities contributing to this exposure. Second, our study comprises of an experiment to test the effectiveness of tailored heat-mitigation recommendations in enhancing participants' knowledge, thereby empowering them as informed citizens, and enabling their effective participation in public initiatives and policymaking.

2 Addressing Vulnerability to Urban Heat & Empowerment

2.1 Main research aim

We aim to comprehensively address the impact of the urban heat island (UHI) effect on vulnerable urban residents in the Netherlands and develop strategies for heat mitigation and adaptation that enhance their quality of life.

2.2 Heat-related challenges

Increased heatwaves and various forms of urban heat exposure, resulting from the accumulation of heat in cities due to UHI, have garnered attention in the Netherlands, particularly due to their impact on the mortality rate among the elderly population (Bergh et al., 2022; Botzen et al., 2020; Daanen et al., 2013; van Loenhout et al., 2018). However, less lethal heat-related issues, like discomfort, reduced productivity, and overall well-being, have received little attention due to data scarcity. Our small, commissioned study with LISS¹ addresses these gaps by examining these concerns. However, given that the exposure to heat can vary significantly

1. Small study launched September 2023.

from year to year, an extension of our existing LISS study will be necessary to incorporate longitudinal data analysis, allowing us to account for temporal differences and track the evolution of these outcomes. Our study will also expand its scope to quantify the impact of these concerns on vulnerable urban residents within their homes and surrounding areas. Our intention is to investigate the underlying causes, including social and spatial disparities such as inadequate insulation, ventilation, and greenery, which contribute to overheating and the UHI effect.

Another aspect of our research will focus on empowering vulnerable participants by providing them with tailored advice for heat mitigation and adaptation aimed at addressing the challenges associated with combating heat in their built environment. While tailored interventions have been widely employed in the fields of Health Sciences and Medicine due to their potential impact on healthcare and patient outcomes, their application in urban heat mitigation and adaptation research is relatively new. Madureira et al. (2021) argue that extensive research on climate risks and warning systems frequently lacks a locally tailored approach to diagnosing risks at the urban subdivision level and fails to offer specific solutions that empower the public to make timely decisions. Moreover, while many Heatwave Early Warning Systems in EU countries offer tailored advice to vulnerable groups, emphasizing behavior adjustments to combat extreme temperatures (Lowe et al., 2011), these recommendations typically do not prioritize measures that actively enhance the cooling of individuals' immediate built environments.

Why is it crucial to provide tailored advice on heat mitigation and adaptation at home for vulnerable groups? Addressing heat concerns in living environment is complex due to several underlying causes, as we will discuss in the next [sub-section](#). We hypothesize that understanding the underlying causes and recognizing the long-term benefits of heat mitigation and adaptation strategies can empower individuals to make well-informed decisions, directly impacting the quality of life for vulnerable populations.

Vulnerable groups, who stand to benefit the most from active participation in democratic processes, often find themselves disconnected from the political landscape. This disconnect stems from ineffective communication between these groups and public actors, resulting in inadequate responses to their concerns (Bovens & Wille, 2017). Implementing educational initiatives, particularly among the youth, regardless of their socio-economic backgrounds, can disrupt the cycle of exclusion and inequality (Hoskins et al., 2017; Hoskins & Janmaat, 2019). This study intends to foster public participation in vulnerable groups, instilling confidence and providing a voice to reduce disparities and enhance well-being.

2.3 Vulnerability to excessive indoor heat

Understanding why houses overheat is complex. The three primary factors contributing to overheating include excessive sunlight exposure due to building orientation and lack of shading, inadequate ventilation (both mechanical and natural), and low thermal mass

combined with insufficient insulation (Samuelson et al., 2020; Thomson et al., 2019). Other factors, such as environmental effects (e.g., UHI), internal heat generation, and occupant behavior, collectively influence the extent and severity of overheating (Taylor et al., 2023).

Generally, poorly insulated homes tend to become excessively hot (Maracchini et al., 2022; Thomson et al., 2019). In a report by TNO, 48% of Dutch households have moderate or poor insulation and about 75% of energy-poor households reside in social housing (Mulder et al., 2023). The demand for air conditioning would enhance the risk of energy poverty. Paradoxically, well-insulated homes also face overheating issues (Kazmi et al., 2022; Ortiz et al., 2020). To combat this, the Dutch Government introduced the TO_{juli} standard² for new constructions since 2021 (RVO, 2019), but the problem persists for older buildings, making it more extensive than initially imagined.

2.4 Vulnerability to excessive outdoor heat

Elevated temperatures in urban areas can lead to negative consequences in outdoor environments. In cities, extreme heat is not spread uniformly but concentrates in densely developed areas. Low-income neighborhoods with low quality greenspaces and proximity to busy streets tend to suffer more health problems from extreme heat (Norton et al., 2015). Moreover, excessive sunlight can increase ground-level ozone, especially in urban areas with high pollution. Such phenomena poses health risks, particularly for vulnerable individuals like the elderly and those with existing health conditions (RIVM, n.d.).

3 Methodological approaches

3.1 Requested sample

We would like to repeat our September 2023 LISS Urban Heat survey with 2,000 participants, maintaining consistency among previous panel members and adhering to a 5-minute time limit³. Our sample composition will be based on address density per km², categorized as extremely urban (2,500), very urban (1,500 – 2,500), and urban (1,000 – 1,500), with a limit of one respondent per household to diversify housing and environmental conditions. We would like to conduct two additional study waves in September 2024 and 2025, following consultation with CentERdata.

3.2 Longitudinal Analysis (Study 1)

To achieve the first objective of our study, the LISS panel data will be linked to the CBS microdata to examine various outcomes at the address level. We are interested in a broad range of outcome variables at the individual level, including thermal discomfort, sleep deprivation, personal productivity (from the LISS questionnaire on Urban Heat), and pollution exposure

2. TO_{juli} standard for heat mitigation are categorized as active, involving mechanical methods like air conditioning, and passive, relying on blocking solar heat gains and ensuring adequate ventilation.

3. The fielded survey also focused on perception of heatwave. Some items from this section will be replaced by new content for the RCT (experiment).

(from RIVM and KNMI database). We will use longitudinal data analysis to account for temporal fluctuations because the degree of heat exposure can vary significantly from year to year. Using this method, we can examine how these results have changed over time. In addition to temperature-related factors, we will control for existing chronic illness (from the LISS questionnaire on Health), satisfaction with their immediate surroundings, and other housing characteristics (from the LISS questionnaire on Economic Situation: Housing).

3.3 Randomized Control Trial (Study 2: Experiment Phase 1)

Our second study aim involves conducting a Randomized Control Trial (RCT), to be fielded in September 2024 and September 2025 over two phases. We will also consult with CentERdata regarding random treatment assignment⁴ and the design of the RCT. In first phase of our study, the intervention group will receive tailored information about effective heat mitigation solutions shortly before the onset of summer, including details about relevant initiatives addressing heat-related challenges. Solutions will encompass a range of cost-effective options, from simple measures like appropriate timings to open windows to more substantial investments like installing external shading devices or insulation. To ensure effective communication to participants, we plan to simplify the information and make use of visual communication (possibly via a web application⁵).

To assess the intervention's impact, we will evaluate self-reported temperature changes, discomfort levels, and sleep quality. We also plan to assess whether they have benefited from distilling the tailored information. We will develop a recommendation algorithm that takes into consideration the specific characteristics of each household (i.e., housing and built environment characteristics, as well as their behaviors and other relevant attributes), and suggests appropriate cooling measures.

3.4 Follow-up Survey (Study 2: Phase 2)

In the second phase of our study, our objective is to assess the long-term impacts of the intervention, specifically focusing on their effectiveness in mitigating heat-related disparities. To achieve this, we will design a follow-up survey to be fielded in September 2025. Through this survey, we will gather essential data on whether participants have undertaken actions such as making investments or engaging in public initiatives aimed at reducing heat in their built environment. This data will enable us to gauge the sustained, real-world effectiveness of the tailored information provided during the initial phase of the study (see [appendix](#) for a preview of preliminary survey questions).

4. In the random allocation, we must maintain balance between participants in the treatment and control groups, aiming for an equal distribution of households, encompassing both renters and homeowners, along with individuals classified as vulnerable.

5. A web application would allow participants to access personalized recommendations, links to public initiatives, real-time temperature and UHI feedback for their surroundings; to achieve this, we plan to collaborate with TU Delft Digital Competence Center.

3.5 The use of CBS microdata

This study is a part of TU Delft PhD research on urban heat inequality, which is affiliated with the [Pandemic and Disaster Preparedness Center](#)⁶ (PDPC) convergence. The PDPC unites over 75 scientists, including partnerships with CBS and experts from various institutes globally, to collaborate. We are currently working on an application to gain access to microdata to evaluate outcomes at participants address-level.

4 Implications for research, practice, and society

This study holds significant implications for society, practice, and future research, enriching our understanding of multi-dimensional aspects of inequality exacerbated by climate risk of heat. Studies into cooling poverty in Europe are in their early stages and exhibit a lack of preparedness, except for the Mediterranean area, when it comes to dealing with summer heat. (Thomson 2019). The insights gained from this study will enrich the existing body of literature on heat vulnerabilities, contributing to a more holistic understanding of the mechanisms that perpetuate inequalities within urban settings. Researchers in the domain of climate mitigation and adaptation and social equity can build upon this approach, refining and expanding predictive models to encompass a broader range of climate-related challenges.

Beyond its theoretical significance, the findings of this research hold practical implications that can drive meaningful change in policy and societal approaches. By empowering vulnerable citizens and bringing attention to relevant initiatives, they can take part and potentially influence future policies addressing overheating. Furthermore, there are concerns about the uptake of air conditioning by households in the coming future. In 2018, 6% of Dutch households owned air conditioning (Government of the Netherlands, 2019), though this figure is expected to rise. Surges in electricity demand can potentially strain and disrupt grids (Borghero et al., 2023; Thomson et al., 2019).

The primary dissemination of the findings and novel study will involve publishing multiple papers within scientific peer-reviewed journals. Overall, its publication in these journals has wide-ranging implications, including addressing climate-related disparities, driving policy shifts, and empowering marginalized communities.

6. <https://convergence.nl/pandemic-disaster-preparedness/>

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6 Appendix

6.1 Sample questions

Study 1 utilizes the survey questions from our previous commissioned study conducted with LISS. In contrast, **Study 2** (phase1 + phase 2) requires a set of newly formulated questions, which are currently under development and will undergo revisions. To make room for the questions essential for Study 2, some questions related to heat perception from our existing survey will be removed.

1. Air conditioning is the only effective way to cool my living space(s).				
Strongly Disagree				Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. High summertime temperatures in my neighborhood are a concern.				
Strongly Disagree				Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

For statement 3, the treatment group will receive a heat map (as part of tailored recommendations) that visualizes the percentage of households impacted by urban heat in their neighborhood using color intensity or visual markers.

3. Many people in my neighborhood are affected by heat during the summer.				
Strongly Disagree			Strongly Agree	I don't know
1	2	3	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

For homeowners:

4. If the number of hot days (> 25°C) continue to increase in the Netherlands, what initiative(s) will you prioritize for keeping your home cool ?	
Invest in air condition	Actions you will likely purse: <input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Invest in insulating my home	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all

Invest in mechanical ventilation	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Install external screens on my windows	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Advocate for subsidies (e.g., for external shutters & mechanical ventilation)	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all

For those renting:

5. If the number of hot days (> 25°C) continue to increase in the Netherlands, what initiative(s) will you prioritize for keeping your home cool ?	
	Actions you will likely pursue:
Invest in air condition	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Move to another house which is cooler	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Advocate the establishment of local cooling centers	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Advocate the right for the installing external shades or other cooling systems, which is opposed by your landlord.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
I will do something else	<input type="checkbox"/> What will you do? (text)

For all (both homeowners and renters)

6. If the number of hot days (> 25°C) continue to increase in the Netherlands, what initiative(s) will you prioritize for keeping your neighborhood cool ?	
	Actions you will likely pursue:
Advocate for the municipality to plant more trees in your neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all

Get involved in community-led projects to reduce urban heat in your neighborhood.	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
Promote energy-efficient and sustainable dwelling/building designs in your community	<input type="checkbox"/> Very much <input type="checkbox"/> Very <input type="checkbox"/> Not very <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all
I will do something else	<input type="checkbox"/> What will you do? (text)

7. Have you made any investments for addressing the heat issue in your home?
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

7a. You have indicated Yes; What have you made?

(Answer type: text)

8. Have participated in initiatives that combat the heat issue in your neighborhood?
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

8a. You have indicated Yes; Which initiatives you have participated in?

(Answer type: text)